

The Neue Zürcher Zeitung (NZZ) suppresses a falsification scandal for years

It is known that Jürg Lindecker, one of the four editors of the anthology „Ingenieure bauen die Schweiz. Technikgeschichte aus erster Hand“ (Engineers build Switzerland. A first-hand technical history), published by the Neue Zürcher Zeitung Verlag, forged or falsified at least four essays. Although the publisher is aware of these falsifications, for many years the book has not been withdrawn from circulation. Furthermore, the co-editor Stefan Betschon copied material from a falsification without citing the source. The editorial staff and the management board of the NZZ do not deny the falsification and the fraudulent scandal, but unjustifiably blame the (at the time uninvolved) Schwabe AG (Basel). The falsifications are e.g. in regard to the German computer inventor Konrad Zuse. Jürg Lindecker has remained silent for years. It is surely no accident that the responsible persons, co-editor Stefan Betschon and the publishing manager Hans-Peter Thür, have left the NZZ (prematurely) and NZZ Libro was sold to the Schwabe AG. According to a communication of April 22nd 2024, a prominent international corruption expert and criminal law professor views the matter as “highly problematical”. In my estimation, the management board of the NZZ has failed to act. The NZZ and the associated CH Media de facto suspended the author, who was active for decades as a science journalist for the NZZ. To this day, the publishing house and the editorial staff of the NZZ have neither come to terms with the scandal nor apologized for their mistakes. It is apparent that they do not wish to confront the matter. Because the noble NZZ is a sacred cow, until now no domestic or foreign medium has had the courage to take up the matter. A multi-page review of the book was given on H-Net, Clio-online. In the meantime, the work is no longer available from the publisher, NZZ Libro (April 2025).

Herbert Bruderer

"It is time to be honest", wrote the chief editor of the NZZ, Eric Gujer, on October 30th 2021 in a leading article. This must apply for his own newspaper as well, particularly for a newspaper that denounces the mistakes of our competitors. A falsification scandal occurred at the publishing house in the Falkenstrasse in Zurich, which the NZZ has kept silent to this day. On November 3rd 2021 I asked Eric Gujer for a plausible written statement in regard to this affair. In his answer of November 9th 2021, the attorney Simon Jakob stated that the NZZ was not responsible. The blame was placed on the Schwabe AG (Basel) ab, which now oversees the book program of NZZ Libro, even though all faulty steps were taken by the NZZ AG (before being sold to the Schwabe AG). The newspaper promoted the book in several large-scale advertisements. Stefan Betschon (co-editor and co-author) and Hans-Peter Thür (publishing manager) were employed by the NZZ. The NZZ was the beneficiary of the contributions of the numerous financial sponsors. The work was not published by Schwabe, but by the Neue Zürcher Zeitung publishing house. My reply of November 11th 2021 was never answered. The NZZ has never distanced itself from this dubious book. The editorial staff and the management board lacked the courage to hold the principal perpetrators, Jürg Lindecker, Stefan Betschon, and Hans-Peter Thür, accountable. On February 21st 2022 I informed the management board about the falsification scandal. In his statement of March 1st 2022, the board member Professor Roland Siegwart (ETH Zurich) repeated the absurd opinion of Jakob: "Understandably, I cannot take a position in regard to the accusations which you have brought, since I am neither responsible nor do I have the professional competence to assess the matter." The editorial staff and the management board, which bears the ultimate responsibility for the corporation, do not deny the existence of the falsification scandal. Roland Siegwart authored the foreword for a (largely unconvincing) book of Stefan Betschon, *Meta-Tag. Streifzüge durch die Computerkultur* (Meta-tag, Excursions through the computer culture), 2017, which was also published by NZZ Libro. His

name appears in volume 1 in connection with industrial research (1st edition, page 174. On May 2nd 2023 the Schwabe publishing house wrote: "We are immediately stopping the sales of the book and will act appropriately in this matter. The book was published in 2014, before NZZ Libro became part of the Schwabe Publishing Group by license agreement." Since the takeover by Schwabe, there was once again a change of personnel in the management of the publishing house.

The point of contention is this anthology: Franz Betschon, Stefan Betschon, Jürg Lindecker, Willy Schlachter (editors): *Ingenieure bauen die Schweiz. Technikgeschichte aus erster Hand*, published by the Neue Zürcher Zeitung Verlag, Zurich in 2013 (see Fig. 1). The second, revised edition (2014) is in two volumes.

Fig. 1: Title page of the book "Ingenieure bauen die Schweiz", 2nd edition, volume 1

Falsified alleged memoirs

The text "Blick zurück in die Zukunft. Die Contraves als Vorkämpferin der Digitaltechnik" (View back to the future. Contraves as a pioneer of digital technology) was not written by Max Lattmann, the former Technical Director of the Zurich-based Contraves AG, as was asserted in the text. Lattmann died in 2011, more than 100 years old, and verifiably left no memoirs. This was confirmed by his life partner Walter Gross (Lattmann's life partner from 1971 until his death) in several telephone conversations. In the "Sonntagszeitung" (sunday newspaper of Tamedia) of November 10th 2013, Gross reiterated this statement. The report originated with Barnaby Skinner (at that time with Tamedia and later with the NZZ). The faulty text regarding Contraves was written by Jürg Lindecker, one of the book's authors. In a written communication of August 29th 2012, he admitted that he had written a "eulogy" for Contraves/Lattmann, which was the basis for the published first-hand account. The co-author Stefan Betschon, for many years (formerly) Informatics Editor of the NZZ, was also informed of this. The falsification was therefore known before the book was published. In spite of this, the legal consultant of the NZZ threatened me repeatedly with legal actions (see Fig. 2).

The screenshot shows the website 'infoclio.ch' with the tagline 'Das Schweizer Fachportal für die Geschichtswissenschaften'. The navigation menu includes 'Aktuell', 'Berichte', 'Verzeichnisse', 'Werkzeuge', and 'Projekte'. Below the menu, there is a breadcrumb trail: 'Startseite → Aktuell → Blog'. The main content area features a green header for the article 'Angebliche Zeitzeugenberichte. Gedanken zum Buch "Ingenieure bauen die Schweiz. Technikgeschichte aus erster Hand"'. The article text includes an update from 17.11.13 stating that a criticism by Herbert Bruderer was removed from the website at the request of the NZZ publishing house. The article is categorized under 'Schweiz Rezensionen Ingenieure Technikgeschichte'. The footer of the page shows the date '11. NOVEMBER 2013 / IT'.

Source: [Angebliche Zeitzeugenberichte. Gedanken zum Buch "Ingenieure bauen die Schweiz. Technikgeschichte aus erster Hand" | infoclio.ch](#)

Fig. 2: Under pressure from the NZZ publishing house, the criticism on info.clio, the specialized portal supported by the Swiss Academy of the Humanities and Social Sciences ([SAGW](#)), was deleted. A detailed review of the book then appeared on Clio-online: Herbert Bruderer: Review of the book: Franz Betschon, Stefan Betschon, Jürg Lindecker, Willy Schlachter (editors): Ingenieure bauen die Schweiz. Technikgeschichte aus erster Hand, Zurich, Verlag Neue Zürcher Zeitung, 2013:

[Review of: F. Betschon et al. \(editor\): Technikgeschichte aus erster Hand | infoclio - reviews](#)

There are contradictions between the printed resume in Lattmann's doctoral dissertation and Lindecker's text: The dissertation indicates that Lattmann interrupted his studies at the ETH Zurich. In the version of Lindecker, Lattmann undertook further studies in Berlin. This depiction speaks, for example, of a lifelong friendship between the German computer inventor Konrad Zuse and Max Lattmann, about which neither Lattmann's life partner of several decades Walter Gross nor Professor Horst Zuse, Konrad Zuse's oldest son, knew nothing. In the 5th unrevised edition of his memoirs Konrad Zuse: Der Computer – Mein Lebenswerk (Konrad Zuse. The Computer – My Life), published by the Springer-Verlag, Berlin, Heidelberg in 2010, Konrad Zuse makes no mention of Lattmann. Furthermore, there is no trace of the Zuse portraits which Lattmann is supposed to have received or purchased. Lindecker in fact asserts that Hermann Göring wished to win over Lattmann – a foreign student – during the time of his studies in Berlin for the research department of the Air Force, which was in fact a secret service.

According to the Hungarian electrical engineer Peter Toth, Lindecker's assertion that Toth had to "flee from his homeland, because he had fought against the red army in the front lines" belongs to the realm of fantasy." Toth built the first Swiss transistorized computer (Cora). In this context, Lindecker's references to the hot transistors are also absurd from a technical standpoint, which in the

opinion of Toth cannot have come from Lattmann in view of his knowledge. Furthermore, the "first-hand account" in regard to Contraves includes unauthorized material from Wikipedia.

The simulated memoirs contain numerous false and in part fictitious assertions. Thus, one reads: "In his search for financial backers, Zuse contacted me [Max Lattmann] in 1948 and suggested that Contraves should acquire the Z4." [...]. "I [Max Lattmann] passed the responsibility for this matter to my supervisor Brändli and my doctoral student colleague Werner Lindecker, who then together with Professor Eduard Stiefel and his assistant Hans Künzi evaluated the Z4 in detail." In the second edition of the book, these unfounded false assertions were repeated.

Eduard Stiefel was the Director of the Institut für angewandte Mathematik (Institute of Applied Mathematics) of the ETH Zurich, founded in 1948, and Hans Brändli was the Director of the Contraves AG in Zurich. Werner Lindecker, Jürg Lindecker's father, was the Technical Director of Paillard SA (Yverdon/Sainte-Croix VD). The (leased) Z4 relay machine was in operation at the ETH Zurich from 1950 to 1955. This computer is considered to be the first functional punched card driven computer in mainland Europe. At the same time, another plugboard controlled computer (the Bark) was in operation in Sweden.

The School Board Minutes of the ETH of October 6th 1949 show that the ETH Zurich first learned about the existence of the Z4 in the summer of 1949. Künzi (University of Zurich) was not an assistant of Stiefel. In the records of the ETH referred to above and a memorandum of the President of the Swiss School Board Hans Pallmann from July 18th 1949, and – as recently gained knowledge shows – for the year 1949 the guest book of Konrad Zuse mentions only Stiefel, Brändli, and Lattmann. Lindecker and Künzi were not present during the inspection of the Z4 on July 13th 1949 in the German village of Hopferau im Allgäu (Bavaria). There is no mention of Lattmann in Zuse's memoirs.

The document properties of Lindecker's Microsoft Word files for Contraves und Paillard (see Fig. 3) contain *exactly the same entries*: Author: Geneva Consulting; Omnisec AG. This is also proof that Lindecker, and not Lattmann, was the author of the text Contraves text. The name Lindecker occurred a number of times in the media in recent times in connection with a secret service affair involving the cryptographic company Omnisec. Jürg Lindecker (born in 1940) is a dazzling electrical engineer from the Swiss village of Greifensee ZH. He is a permanent guest of honor at the ETH Zurich and Honorary President of the ETH Alumni. Along with two other co-editors (Franz Betschon and Willy Schlachter), he is or was a member of the Giardino military group.

Fig. 3: Document properties in Lindecker's portrayals of Contraves and Paillard

Incorrect addendum in the 2nd edition

The 2nd edition of the book contains the following addendum: "With the support of Jürg Lindecker, in the last months of his life Max Lattmann drafted an autobiographical text. He died on May 10th 2011 before this book was printed and could therefore no longer have authorized the shortened and revised version of his text published here." These assertions do not conform to the truth. As an example: In the unabridged version of the fictitious memoirs the text reads: "In this probationary time I was extremely pushed to my physical limits – which resulted in my suffering from optical tuberculosis and compelled me to pause for a year: Fortunately, the doctors of the Ophthalmological Hospital in Davos were able to save the vision of the left eye, but from then on I was blind in the right eye." According to Walter Gross, this assertion is unfounded, and the false assertion cannot be ascribed to Lattmann.

Professor Hans Dieter Hellige (University of Bremen), a leading German historian of informatics, characterizes the portrayal of Contraves as an "extremely crude falsification" and a "malevolent concoction." A well-known technological historian from Berlin, who is active in connection with the world's largest computer museum, views certain narratives as "from beginning to end purely invention." In the fictitious memoirs, numerous sections were taken from Wikipedia without reference to the sources.

Questionable report regarding Paillard

It was no accident that the faulty paper "Von der Musikdose zur Federwerk-Filmkamera. Aufstieg und Fall von Paillard" (From the musical box to the spring-driven film camera. The rise and fall of Paillard) of Jürg Lindecker, with three illustrations from the private archive of J. D. Lindecker, was replaced by a text of Dominik Landwehr in the second edition.

A further falsification?

The essay "Fernsehbilder im Kino. Mit dem Eidophor beeindruckt die Gretag Hollywoodgrößen" (Television images in the movie theater. Gretag impresses the Hollywood Greats with the Eidophor) of Hugo Thiemann also derives very likely from Jürg Lindecker. Thiemann died in 2012 at the age of 95 before the book was printed. The depiction includes, for example, an illustration from the private archive of J. and M. Lindecker. The author claims that John Steinbeck worked with a Hermes Baby (a portable typewriter from Paillard, in Yverdon). The same assertion is found in Lindecker's portrayal of Paillard (1st edition). Thiemann was the president of the management board of Geneva Consulting. This company is also mentioned in the document properties of Lindecker's Microsoft Word files.

Copied from a falsification without citing the source

Another questionable contribution is "Der Zauber des Anfangs. Schweizer Computerpioniere" (The fascinating beginning. Swiss computer pioneers) of Stefan Betschon. On pages 378–379 (1st edition) Betschon propagates the same absurdity as Lindecker in the falsified alleged memoirs of Lattmann (page 432). Here there are contradictions relating to the resume printed in Lattmann's dissertation (1939). Betschon also reiterates similar falsified information (invented by Lindecker) on page 399. In the 2nd edition, certain unfounded assertions lifted from elsewhere have been largely deleted (pages 380–381). The remaining false assertions are still propagated in the 2nd edition (page 401). Stefan Betschon writes: "With the explicit restriction that the machine was to be used only for technical and scientific purposes, at the end of 1949 the Swiss School Board approved a credit of 30,000 Swiss Francs for the leasing of the Z4". According to the minutes of the Swiss School Board from that time, there was no such restriction, nor was the Swiss School Board responsible for this decision. The maintenance costs amounted to 50,000 Swiss Francs, and the leasing costs were only a part of these.

Imaginary memoirs of Alan Turing from A to Z

Jürg Lindecker offered the manuscript not only to the Verlag Neue Zürcher Zeitung, but also (inadmissibly) offered me the same manuscript for publication. A from A to Z fabricated comprehensive account of the life of Alan Turing was supposed to be included in the book commemorating the 100th birthday of Konrad Zuse. With the help of the leading international Turing experts, the swindle was exposed. If we had been taken in, the book would have had to be destroyed. The British mathematician is considered to be the founder of theoretical computer science. The A. M. Turing Award conferred by the Association for Computing Machinery (New York) is considered the "Nobel prize of computing". I am not aware of whether this unscrupulous essay was ever published anywhere. Because the correctness and authenticity of the texts had to be meticulously appraised, the editorial revision required for the two fictitious memoirs (Lattmann and Turing) was enormously time-consuming,

More than 20 financial backers, and more than 50 contributors

The scandal is all the more embarrassing in view of the fact that more than 20 persons supported the comprehensive work financially, among them ETH Alumni, the ETH Board, Georg Fischer, the Hasler Foundation, Metrohm, Stadler, Swisscom, and Swissmem. The disingenuous portrayals are also a serious imposition with respect to the other more than 50 authors from industry, the economy and science who contributed text material.

First-hand accounts?

The subtitle "Technikgeschichte aus erster Hand" (A first-hand technical history) indicates that contemporary witnesses report on their experiences. However, this only partly applies. Thus, for example, the co-author Franz Betschon is immediately represented with five contributions. For instance, he writes about the Albulabahn railway stretch, opened more than 100 years ago (!). Many texts could just as well have been written by good, uninvolved technical journalists. In the second volume as well, there are contributions which are not first-hand and were not written by contemporary witnesses.

Concluding remarks

It is incomprehensible why the three co-editors, all of whom were also co-authors, did not see through their colleague Lindecker. And it is surely no accident that the second volume no longer gives *Lindecker either as editor or as author*. That the fainthearted publishing house did not (promptly) withdraw the work from circulation is unexplainable.

Under the name "Betschon" only a single work of this author is mentioned on the NZZ Libro Website (see Fig. 4).

Es wurden 2 Produkte für „Betschon“ gefunden.

Lieferbarkeit Ausgabeart

2 von 500 Büchern

Fig. 4: Entry on the NZZ Libro Website (April 2025).

However, the two-volume work on the history of technology has vanished without a trace from the publishing house (see Fig. 5). It is still present on Amazon.

Leider konnten wir nichts unter „Ingenieure bauen die Schweiz“ finden.

Überprüfen Sie Ihre Eingabe oder versuchen Sie es mit einem anderen Stichwort. Wissen Sie noch nicht genau wonach Sie suchen? Schauen Sie sich unsere Bestseller an.

Fig. 5: Unsuccessful search on the NZZ Libro Website (April 2025).

Translated from the German by Dr. John McMinn

Sources

The following work discusses the events of these times in detail (see Fig. 6).

Fig. 6: Cover pictures of the German and English versions of the "Milestones", volume 1

Bruderer, Herbert: Meilensteine der Rechentechnik, De Gruyter Oldenbourg, Berlin/Boston, 3. Auflage 2020, Band 1, 970 Seiten, 577 Abbildungen, 114 Tabellen,

<https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110669664> und [Band 1+2 \[Set Meilensteine der Rechentechnik, Band 1+2\] \(degruyter.com\)](#)

Bruderer, Herbert: Meilensteine der Rechentechnik, De Gruyter Oldenbourg, Berlin/Boston,
3. Auflage 2020, Band 2, 1055 Seiten, 138 Abbildungen, 37 Tabellen,
<https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110669671> und [Band 1+2 \[Set Meilensteine der Rechentechnik,
Band 1+2\] \(degruyter.com\)](#)

Bruderer, Herbert: Milestones in Analog and Digital Computing, Springer Nature Switzerland AG,
Cham, 3rd edition 2020, 2 volumes, 2113 pages, 715 illustrations, 151 tables, translated from the
German by Dr. John McMinn, <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-40974-6>

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